

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

20250318-ProCleanLakes-

**Hungry Catfish—Effect of Prey
Availability on Movement**

Dynamics of a Top Predator-V01

**Funded by
the European Union**

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Reason(s) for data analysis: *Scientific publication analysing the effect of prey availability on movement dynamics of a top predator – European catfish.*

Creation date of file(s): 2/2025

Used method(s): *Acoustic telemetry monitoring of 45 tagged individuals of European catfish in 3 different water bodies.*

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- *Locations of individual fish were calculated using proprietary post-processing software UMAP v.1.4.3 (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Canada). Filtering and further post-processing of fish locations are described in detail in Říha et al. (2021).*
- *The extent of horizontal area use was calculated using a 95% kernel utilisation distribution (hereafter referred to as KUD).*
- *To investigate catfish space use and activity in the three waterbodies, a Generalised Additive Mixed (GAM) model was created.*

Data:

- *activity_for_model.csv - Catfish swimming activity (expressed in m/sec) by date and day hour in the three studied waterbodies - Milada Lake, Most Lake and Rimov Reservoir.*
- *hungry_wels_kernel95.csv - Space utilisation of catfish, expressed as 95% kernel utilization distribution (hectares) in the daily interval in the three studied waterbodies - Milada Lake, Most Lake and Rimov Reservoir.*
- *hungry_wels_kernel95_dp.csv - Space utilisation of catfish, expressed as 95% kernel utilization distribution (hectares) by day and diel period in the three studied waterbodies - Milada Lake, Most Lake and Rimov Reservoir.*
- *hungry_wels_pelprop_dp.csv - Catfish utilisation of the open water habitat (expressed as proportion of individual locations in open water) by date and diel period in the three studied waterbodies - Milada Lake, Most Lake and Rimov Reservoir.*

Code:

NA

Additional files:

activity_for_model.csv

hungry_wels_kernel95.csv

hungry_wels_kernel95_dp.csv

hungry_wels_pelprop_dp.csv

License:

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Notes:

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